

Fertilizer-derived uranium uptake in maize (*Zea mays* L.): Findings from pot and field experiments in Tanzania

Nils Haneklaus^{a,b,c,d,*}, Dennis A. Mwalongo^e, Najat K. Mohammed^e, Jacob B. Lisuma^f, Hendrik Brink^g, Hupenyu A. Mupambwa^h, Hamid Mazouzⁱ, Viktoriia Chubur^j, Hynek Roubík^j, Guangfei Qu^k, Stanisław Waclawek^l, Kelvin M. Mtei^b

^a Faculty of Earth Sciences, Geography and Astronomy, University of Vienna, 1090 Vienna, Austria

^b Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology (NM-AIST), School for Materials, Energy, Water, Environmental Science and Engineering P.O. Box 447, Arusha, Tanzania

^c North-West University, Unit for Energy and Technology Systems - Nuclear Engineering, 11 Hoffman Street, Potchefstroom 2520, South Africa

^d University for Continuing Education Krems, Td-Lab Sustainable Mineral Resources, Dr.-Karl-Dorrek-Straße 30, 3500 Krems an der Donau, Austria

^e Tanzania Atomic Energy Commission, P. O. Box 1585, Dodoma, Tanzania

^f Tobacco Research Institute of Tanzania (TORITA), Research Department, P.O. Box 431, Tumbi, 45120, Tabora, Tanzania

^g Department of Chemical Engineering, University of Pretoria, Pretoria, 0002, South Africa

^h Sam Nujoma Marine and Coastal Resources Research Centre, Sam Nujoma Campus, University of Namibia, P. Box 462, Henties Bay, Namibia

ⁱ Expertise Center for Phosphate (CEPH), Mohammed VI Polytechnic University (UM6P), Ben Guerir 43150, Morocco

^j Department of Food and BioResource Technology, Faculty of Tropical AgriSciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Prague, Czech Republic

^k Faculty of Environmental Science and Engineering, Kunming University of Science and Technology, Kunming, Yunnan, 650500, China

^l Institute for Nanomaterials, Advanced Technologies, and Innovation, Technical University of Liberec, Liberec, Czech Republic

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ABSTRACT

Phosphate fertilizers can introduce uranium (U) into agricultural soils and potentially into edible crop tissues. This work evaluated U transfer from fertilizers into maize (*Zea mays* L.) under Tanzanian field and pot conditions. Three fertilizers with contrasting intrinsic U concentrations (39–160 mg kg⁻¹) were assessed in a single-season field experiment and in a replicated pot experiment, together with measurements of calcium (Ca) and exploratory bark and kaolin amendment treatments to mitigate U transfer from soil to plant. In the field experiments, interpreted descriptively, U concentrations were highest in soil (2.07–3.96 mg kg⁻¹), intermediate in roots (0.99–2.20 mg kg⁻¹), stems (0.39–1.09 mg kg⁻¹), and leaves (0.17–0.48 mg kg⁻¹), and lowest in grain (0.09–0.26 mg kg⁻¹, ash basis). In the pot experiment, one-way ANOVA showed highly significant treatment effects for U in soil, root, stem, and leaf compartments (all $p < 0.001$), and fertilizer/amendment interactions were significant among fertilized pots, indicating treatment-specific responses. Transfer coefficients for U and Ca supported a consistent partitioning pattern of soil > root > stem \approx leaf > grain and showed that U transfer to grain remained strongly attenuated in both systems. Several amendment treatments, particularly kaolin and tree bark sawdust, were associated with reduced U concentrations and reduced transfer beyond the root compartment in the pot experiments, although no mechanistic measurements were made. Overall, the results identified fertilizer sources and compartmental partitioning as key controls on maize U accumulation and provided regionally relevant baseline data for exposure assessment and for future testing of low-cost retention measures under field-relevant conditions.

1. Introduction

Global soil pollution by toxic metals threatens agriculture and human health (Hou et al., 2025). Mineral fertilizers, derived from

phosphate ore, can contain radiotoxic uranium (U) (e Silva and de Oliveira, 2023; Haneklaus, 2021; Schnug and Lottermoser, 2013). Although U does not have a nutritional value to plants, it can result in plant uptake that usually (linearly until saturation) increases with

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: nils.haneklaus@univie.ac.at (N. Haneklaus).

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increased U availability in soil (Chen et al., 2021). The amount of U found in mineral fertilizers is largely dependent on the phosphate ore used to produce the applied fertilizers, with smaller variations associated to the specific processing conditions (Bilal et al., 2023). Minjingu phosphate ore from Tanzania is known for its relatively high phosphorus pentoxide (P_2O_5) grade, and relatively high U concentrations that can reach values of more than 400 mg U kg^{-1} phosphate ore (Haneklaus et al., 2024; Mwalongo et al., 2024, 2023b), so that the material could theoretically also be qualified as a commercial very low-grade U ore (Haneklaus et al., 2017; Ud-Din Khan et al., 2024). The use of fertilizers produced from Minjingu phosphate ore was recently found to increase the radioactivity of tobacco plants in Kenya, Tanzania and Uganda (Mwalongo et al., 2023a). It needs to be emphasized that the measured radioactivity, though increased compared to tobacco grown with other fertilizers, was still well within legal limits, and it is further relevant that tobacco is known for its increased U uptake so that the plant is even used as a hyperaccumulator for phytoremediation (John et al., 2022; Stojanović et al., 2012).

Unlike tobacco, which is consumed by choice for pleasure, Maize (*Zea mays* L., corn) provides approximately 60% of dietary intake for most Tanzanians (De Groot et al., 2013; FAO, 2015; Gebre et al., 2021) and plain maize porridge is a common infant food in the country, consumed daily by more than 90% of children (Mlilo et al., 2007). For food security globally, maize is by far the most important crop, providing roughly double the amount of dried grain as wheat and rice (Erenstein et al., 2022). In Tanzania, maize is also a cash crop, accounting for over 45% of total arable land and contributing nearly 50% of cash revenue in rural regions (FAOSTAT, 2021). The crop is widely grown in the Southern- (Iringa, Mbeya, Songwe, Njombe, and Ruvuma) and Northern- (Tanga and Arusha) Highland regions. NPK (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium) fertilizers such as YaraMila Cereal (YM), Minjingu Nafaka Plus (NP) or locally produced ground phosphate ore concentrate (Minjingu Powder, MP) are mineral fertilizers commonly used on the relatively acidic soils found in Tanzania and other East African regions to increase maize yields.

Previous pot experiments with maize (*Zea mays* L.) suggest that only 1-10% of fertilizer derived available U transfers to the plant stem (Heshmati-Rafsanjani, 2009) from where even less transfers to the grains/seeds that are ultimately consumed. These studies do, however, acknowledge that local conditions could significantly alter U uptake and should therefore be assessed on a case-by-case basis. Stojanović et al. (2013, 2010) further suggested that increased soil acidity could even increase U uptake of maize. The potential connection between heavy metals uptake and soil acidity is a finding particularly relevant for Tanzania as well as other parts of East Africa, where increased soil acidity is not uncommon.

The objective of this study was not only to document U concentrations in different maize compartments, but to also test whether simple amendment treatments could influence the transfer of fertilizer-derived U from soil into maize tissues under Tanzanian field and pot conditions. Specifically, we asked whether: (i) fertilizers with higher intrinsic U contents are associated with higher U concentrations in soil and maize tissues, (ii) U shows a consistent partitioning pattern from soil to roots to aboveground organs and ultimately grain, and (iii) low-cost amendments such as untreated kaolin and tree bark sawdust can reduce tissue U concentrations under controlled pot conditions.

This work assessed the U uptake of maize in Tanzania from three commonly used mineral fertilizers (YM, NP and MP) as well as a control group (no fertilization) using field- and pot experiments. Calcium (Ca) availability reportedly influences U uptake (Mertens et al., 2022; Sathou et al., 2022), so the Ca availability and uptake were also documented here. Clay minerals and sawdust, used independently or together, are inexpensive applications that are commonly believed to retain heavy metals, thus reducing plant uptake (Adegoke et al., 2022; Irfan et al., 2021; Otunola and Olojede, 2020). Kaolin clay powder (Pugu Hills, Tanzania) and Maiden's gum (*Eucalyptus globulus* ssp *maidenii*) tree

bark sawdust were used together and independently in the pot experiments to test this hypothesis.

2. Materials and methods

Hybrid maize seeds Dekalb variety DKC 8053 were purchased from Monsanto Seed Company Ltd. and certified by the Tanzania Official Seed Certification Institute (TOSCI). The seed variety was chosen since it is commonly used by farmers in Tanzania as well as other parts of East- and Southern Africa due to the higher yields obtained from it. Three fertilizers, YaraMila cereal (YM) (N: 23%, P_2O_5 : 10%, K_2O : 5%, S: 3%, MgO: 2%, Zn: 0.3%, and U: 38.84 ± 1.24 mg kg^{-1}), Minjingu Nafaka plus (NP) (N: 9%, P_2O_5 : 16%, K_2O : 6%, CaO: 25%, S: 5%, MgO: 2%, Zn: 0.5%, B: 0.1% and U: 147.65 ± 8.61 mg kg^{-1}) and Minjingu Powder (MP) (P_2O_5 : 28% and U: 159.67 ± 10.48 mg kg^{-1}) were used in this work. Besides, we included a control group without fertilizer use.

Eucalyptus globulus ssp *maidenii* bark is a waste product in Tanzania and was obtained from local timber producers. Kaolin was collected from Pugu hills, Kisarawe district in the Pwani region, Tanzania (China et al., 2019). Sawdust and clay powder were applied as solid soil amendments in the pot experiment. The required quantities (50 g per pot for each material) were accurately weighed prior to application. For individual treatments, either sawdust and kaolin were added, while in combined treatments both materials (50 g each) were first mixed and homogenized. The amendments were then thoroughly incorporated into the soil in each pot to ensure uniform distribution within the root zone and maximize interaction with soil particles.

All experiments were conducted in the November-2021/April-2022 cropping season. Pot experiments were conducted at Nelson Mandela African Institution of Science and Technology (NM-AIST) at Nambala ward located at S 3° 21' 56", E 36° 40' 28" in Arusha region and field experiments were conducted at an experimental site of the Tobacco Research Institute of Tanzania (TORITA) located at S 05° 04' 02.5" and E 032° 06' 09.7", at Tumbi ward in the Tabora region using a split-split randomized completed block design (SSCRBD).

The maize was cultivated in ridges based on local farmers' practices. The size of each experimental plot was 6m x 6m with ridge spacing of 75 cm, which led to 4 ridges per plot, with 16 plants per ridge at 30 cm plant spacing, resulting in a total of 64 plants per plot. Two times 10 g of fertilizer was applied per plant during the first two weeks after sowing. Another 15 g was applied four weeks after seedlings emerged and another 15 g per plant was given before tasseling. In total 50 g of fertilizer was thus applied per plant. In the case of the control group, no fertilizer was given. To avoid any influence of previously used fertilizers, the field experiments at TORITA were conducted on lands that had not been farmed for over ten years. The pot experiments used identical amounts of fertilizers and distilled water, while rainwater (approximately 950 mm annually) was used in the field experiments. The field experiments were conducted once. The pot experiments were conducted in triplicate and averaged values were reported here.

Field experiments were carried out on sandy loam soil (pH: 7.38 ± 0.52 ; organic carbon 12.93 ± 0.19 g kg^{-1} , and CEC: 30.90 ± 1.29 mmol⁺ kg^{-1}) while pot experiments were carried out with loamy sand soil with slightly different characteristics (pH: 7.23 ± 0.10 ; organic carbon 12.34 ± 0.29 g/kg, and CEC: 21.22 ± 1.27 mmol⁺ kg^{-1}). After plant growth, soil from each pot was sampled from the surface to 30 cm depth using a soil auger (76 cm diameter). The samples were subsampled for subsequent analysis. Five samples of 1 kg soil were taken from each plot, considering the different treatments. Plant samples, and here specifically roots, stems, leaves and grains were taken from the same points where the soil was collected. Maize grains were soaked in distilled water for three hours and washed to eliminate any foreign materials such as soil and dust. Root samples were soaked in distilled water for three hours as well and completely washed to reduce potential contamination of the root samples from the soil. Samples were subsequently oven-dried in a clean and dust-free environment at 105 °C until a constant weight was

reached. Plant samples were then weighed and incinerated at 350 °C for 5 hours in a dry crucible placed in a muffle furnace. The resulting ash samples were again weighed and placed in an airtight bag to prevent the accumulation of moisture before the ash was analyzed for U and Ca. Unless otherwise stated, plant U and Ca concentrations reported in this study are expressed on an ash-mass basis because tissues were dry-ashed prior to digestion and inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) analysis.

A total of 91 soil and plant (root, stem, leaf and grain) samples from pot and field experiments were prepared and analyzed for this study. 0.1 g of an aliquot of the sample was microwave digested in an acid mixture (3 mL HNO₃ ultrapure 60% + 5 ml HF 40%) at high pressure and temperature (speedwave, Berghof Products + Instruments GmbH, Eningen, Germany). Nitric acid and ultra-pure hydrofluoric acid were used. The solution was transferred to 50 ml flasks after ambient cooling and delivered to the desired volume with high purity water. The measurements were conducted using ICP-MS (NexION 300D, Perkin Elmer, Waltham, MA, USA). The quality of the measured results was checked and rechecked using standard reference materials from the U.S. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST 1570a) and the U.S. Geological Survey (BCR-2) for soil.

Statistical analyses were conducted separately for the field and pot experiments. Because the field experiment was performed during a

single cropping season and the available field observations represent subsamples within treatment plots rather than clearly independent replicated plots, field concentrations are presented descriptively. For the pot experiment, replicate-level concentrations were analyzed for soil, root, stem and leaf compartments using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) across the 13 treatment groups (control as well as each fertilizer and amendment combination). This was used as the primary inferential analysis because the control treatment did not include amendment levels and therefore the full factorial design was incomplete. As a secondary analysis, fertilized pots only were evaluated by two-way ANOVA with fertilizer type and amendment treatment as fixed factors to assess fertilizer/amendment interactions. When significant effects were detected, Tukey's honestly significant difference (HSD) test was used for pairwise comparisons. Grain U concentrations in the pot experiments were not analyzed inferentially because most values were at or near the analytical detection limit. Transfer coefficients were calculated descriptively to support interpretation of U and Ca partitioning among soil and plant compartments. Statistical significance was assessed at $p < 0.05$.

To support interpretation of element partitioning, transfer coefficients were calculated as concentration ratios between successive compartments (root/soil, stem/root, leaf/root, and grain/root) for U and Ca. Field transfer coefficients were interpreted descriptively,

Fig. 1. Field concentrations of uranium (top) and calcium (bottom), ash basis, in soil and maize compartments from the Tanzania field experiment. Bars show mean values and error bars show standard deviation of the measured replicates. Because the field study was conducted during a single season and the uploaded files did not document independent replicated field plots for each fertilizer treatment, these data are presented descriptively only. Abbreviations: YM, YaraMila; NP, Nafaka Plus; MP, Minjing Powder.

whereas pot transfer coefficients were derived from replicate-level data and used to support treatment comparisons.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Field experiments

Because the field experiment was conducted in a single cropping season, the field data are interpreted descriptively. Uranium concentrations were highest in soils (2.07–3.96 mg kg⁻¹) and decreased strongly across maize tissues, with roots and vegetative organs containing

substantially more U than grain (0.09–0.26 mg kg⁻¹; Fig. 1). The field results therefore show a consistent partitioning pattern (soil > root > stem ≈ leaf > grain), while quantitative differences among fertilizer treatments should be interpreted cautiously. Since these values are reported on an ash basis, they are not directly comparable to the dry-weight concentrations that are also reported in the scientific literature without conversion. Nevertheless, the pattern observed here that indicates much lower U in grain than in roots and shoots is consistent with previous studies showing limited soil-to-grain transfer of U in cereal crops.

Ca concentrations were substantially higher in soils than in maize

Fig. 2. Pot uranium concentrations (ash basis) in soil, root, stem, leaf, and grain compartments across fertilizer and amendment treatments. Bars show mean ± SD (n = 3 pots per treatment for soil, root, stem, and leaf; grain uranium remained sparse and is shown descriptively). Different lowercase letters indicate significant differences among treatment groups within a compartment based on one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD (p < 0.05). Control had no amendment treatment. Abbreviations: NP, Nafaka Plus; YM, YaraMila; MP, Minjingu Powder; K, kaolin; B, bark.

tissues, reflecting the role of soil as the dominant Ca reservoir. Among plant organs, Ca concentrations in grain (0.32–1.01 g kg⁻¹ ash) were comparable to or higher than those in some vegetative tissues. Because all plant tissues were dry-ashed prior to analysis, organ-to-organ Ca comparisons should be interpreted with caution: differences in ash yield among roots, stems, leaves and grain can influence concentration values when expressed on an ash basis. Accordingly, the field Ca results are most useful for describing relative partitioning patterns within this dataset rather than for direct comparison with literature values reported on a dry-weight basis.

3.2. Pot experiments

Fig. 2 summarizes U concentrations measured in soil and maize compartments (roots, stems, leaves, and grain) in the controlled pot experiments under different fertilizer and amendment treatments. One-way ANOVA across the 13 pot treatment groups showed highly significant treatment effects for U in soil, root, stem and leaf compartments (all $p < 0.001$). Soil U ranged from approximately 0.64 to 6.21 mg kg⁻¹, with the highest values in Minjingu Powder (MP) and Nafaka Plus (NP) treatments, whereas YaraMila Cereal (YM) remained closer to the unfertilized control. These patterns are consistent with the contrasting U contents of the fertilizers used in this study.

Uranium accumulation in maize roots showed the largest variability among plant compartments, with concentrations ranging from 0.09 to 3.66 mg kg⁻¹. In the fertilized pots, two-way ANOVA indicated a strong fertilizer/amendment interaction for root U ($p < 0.001$), showing that amendment effects depended on fertilizer type. Relative to the corresponding unamended fertilizer treatment, the combined kaolin and tree bark sawdust treatment was associated with marked reductions in root U. Specifically, in Nafaka Plus (-74.4%), Minjingu Powder (-76.5%) and YaraMila Cereal (-70.4%). These results support a strong amendment-associated reduction in root U under pot conditions, but they do not by themselves identify the underlying immobilization mechanism.

Uranium concentrations in above ground tissues were substantially lower than in roots, confirming restricted translocation of U within maize plants. Stem U ranged from approximately 0.01 to 2.63 mg kg⁻¹ and leaf U from values close to 0.01 mg kg⁻¹ to 1.28 mg kg⁻¹, with highly significant treatment effects in both compartments (one-way ANOVA, $p < 0.001$ for each). In the fertilized pots, fertilizer/amendment interactions were also highly significant for stem U ($p < 0.001$) and leaf U ($p < 0.001$). Grain U concentrations remained the lowest among all plant compartments, ranging from values below the detection limit to 0.01 mg kg⁻¹ on an ash basis. Because a lot of published crop concentrations are reported on a dry-weight basis, we avoided direct numerical comparison here unless the reporting basis is aligned. The low grain concentrations nevertheless support the general conclusion of limited translocation of U to edible tissues under the present pot conditions.

A direct inferential comparison between pot and field experiments was not attempted because the two systems differed in scale, soil properties and water regime, and because the field study was not replicated in the same way as the pot experiments were. Nevertheless, both systems showed the same overall rank-order partitioning pattern (soil > root > stem ≈ leaf > grain). Within the pot experiment, amendment-associated reductions in root and shoot U were strongest in several kaolin and tree bark sawdust treatments, particularly for NP and MP, indicating that these low-cost materials warrant further testing under field-relevant conditions. However, no measurements of U speciation, soil solution chemistry or sorption were performed here, so the amendment effects should be interpreted as treatment associations rather than demonstrated mechanisms.

Calcium in the pot experiment also responded significantly to the different treatments. One-way ANOVA showed significant differences among the 13 treatment groups in soil, root, stem, leaf and grain Ca (all $p < 0.001$). Among fertilized pots, fertilizer/amendment interactions were significant for root ($p = 0.0037$), stem ($p < 0.001$), leaf ($p < 0.001$) and

grain ($p < 0.001$) Ca, indicating that amendment-associated changes in Ca partitioning were fertilizer-specific rather than uniform across treatments (Fig. 3).

3.3. Transfer coefficients and compartmental partitioning of U and Ca

To complement the concentration data, transfer coefficients were calculated as concentration ratios between successive compartments (root/soil, stem/root, leaf/root, and grain/root) for both U and Ca (Fig. 4). These ratios were used to summarize the relative movement of elements through the soil-plant system and to compare partitioning patterns between the field and pot experiments. Because the field experiment was conducted in a single season and was interpreted descriptively, transfer coefficients for field samples are presented as pattern-based indicators only, whereas the pot experiment provided the main basis for treatment comparisons.

Across both experiments, U transfer coefficients supported the concentration-based conclusion that U was retained predominantly in soil and roots, with much more limited movement to aerial tissues and especially to grain. In the field experiment, root/soil U transfer remained low overall, while stem/root, leaf/root, and grain/root coefficients indicated progressively reduced transfer toward the edible fraction. A similar overall pattern was observed in the pot experiment, where most treatments showed relatively restricted root-to-shoot translocation and very low grain/root coefficients. This is consistent with previous work showing that U commonly accumulates in roots and often displays limited translocation to shoots and reproductive tissues, particularly in monocot crops such as maize. In maize specifically, U has been reported to accumulate strongly in roots, including root apoplastic compartments and root tips, which may restrict subsequent upward transport. Likewise, comparative soil-plant transfer studies have shown relatively low U transfer to maize compared with some other species (Chen et al., 2005; Straczek et al., 2010).

The transfer-coefficient approach also clarified treatment effects that were less obvious from concentration ranges alone. In the pot experiments, fertilizers with higher intrinsic U contents generally produced higher root/soil transfer and higher root-to-shoot coefficients than the control treatment, suggesting that the fertilizer source influenced not only absolute concentrations but also the internal partitioning of U within the plant. At the same time, most amendment treatments were associated with lower transfer beyond the root compartment, especially when kaolin and tree bark sawdust were combined. This pattern is consistent with reduced U mobility and stronger retention in the soil-root zone under several amended conditions, although the present data do not resolve the underlying mechanism directly.

One notable exception was observed for the bark-only treatment combined with Minjingu Powder, where stem/root and leaf/root U transfer coefficients were substantially higher than in the corresponding unamended treatment. This apparent outlier deserves specific consideration. Importantly, the pattern arose not because total U uptake was universally highest in this treatment, but because root U remained comparatively low while stem and leaf U concentrations were relatively elevated, which inflated the root-to-shoot ratios. A plausible explanation is that bark-derived dissolved organic matter altered U speciation and weakened retention on soil particles or root surfaces, thereby favouring mobilization and upward transport of part of the absorbed U pool. This interpretation is supported by studies showing that organic ligands can strongly influence U chemistry in soils and plant matrices, and that humic substances may decrease U sorption to soils and promote desorption. It is also consistent with broader evidence that U mobility and plant availability are highly sensitive to solution chemistry, including pH, inorganic carbon, and competing ligands. We therefore interpret the bark-only outlier cautiously as evidence that organic amendments do not necessarily immobilize U uniformly; depending on their composition and the surrounding soil solution chemistry, they may either reduce or enhance U mobility (Bednar et al., 2007).

Fig. 3. Pot calcium concentrations (ash basis) in soil, root, stem, leaf, and grain compartments across fertilizer and amendment treatments. Bars show mean \pm SD ($n = 3$ pots per treatment). Different lowercase letters indicate significant differences among treatment groups within a compartment based on one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's HSD ($p < 0.05$). Control had no amendment treatment. Abbreviations: NP, Nafaka Plus; YM, YaraMila; MP, Minjingu Powder; K, kaolin; B, bark.

The Ca transfer coefficients showed a different and generally less restricted pattern than those documented for U. In both experiments, Ca moved more readily from roots to stems, leaves, and grain, reflecting its role as an essential plant nutrient rather than a non-essential trace contaminant. This contrast is useful because it emphasizes that the low grain transfer observed for U was not simply a consequence of poor plant growth or generalized restriction of ion transport. Instead, it supports the interpretation that U and Ca, although potentially linked at the uptake interface, differ markedly in subsequent internal distribution. Recent mechanistic studies have shown that U uptake can involve Ca-permeable cation channels, and that Ca and carbonate chemistry can influence both U bioavailability and root-to-shoot translocation.

However, the present study did not directly test transport pathways or U speciation, so that the Ca data obtained here were interpreted as contextual support rather than mechanistic proof (El Hayek et al., 2019, 2018; Sarthou et al., 2022).

Overall, the transfer coefficients strengthen the interpretation of the concentration data by showing that fertilizer-associated U in maize was governed not only by source concentration, but also by compartment-specific retention and translocation. The dominant pattern in both field and pot systems suggests strong retention in the soil-root continuum and strongly attenuated transfer to grain. From a crop-exposure perspective, this is reassuring in the sense that edible grain remained the compartment with the by far least concentration of U. From a process

Fig. 4. Uranium and calcium transfer coefficients in field and pot experiments. Transfer coefficients were calculated as concentration ratios between successive compartments (root/soil, stem/root, leaf/root, and grain/root). Field values are presented descriptively only, whereas pot values are based on replicate-level data. Colors indicate fertilizer source, and line styles/markers indicate amendment treatment. Grain/root U coefficients in the pot experiment should be interpreted cautiously because several grain U concentrations were at or near the detection limit.

perspective, however, the transfer analysis also shows that amendment effects were treatment-specific and that tree bark sawdust-containing amendments may under some conditions modify U mobility in rather unexpected ways. This reinforces the need to evaluate low-cost mitigation measures not only by total concentration changes but also by how they alter transfer within the soil-plant system.

3.4. Potential health risks

It is noteworthy that there is no legal limit on U concentrations in fertilizers and even legal limits of U in crops are uncommon. A widely referenced benchmark in this context is the World Health Organization (WHO) suggested tolerable daily intake (TDI) of 0.6 μg U per kg body weight per day which was originally set for drinking water (Alexander et al., 2009; WHO, 2012). The highest measured grain U concentration was 0.26 mg kg^{-1} on an ash basis. To relate this value to potential dietary exposure, it was converted using the ash fraction of maize grain as consumed (approximately 1.287%) (INRAE-CIRAD-AFZ, 2024), yielding an estimated concentration in edible grain of approximately 0.0033 mg kg^{-1} (3.3 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) so that an adult (70 kg) or a child (20 kg) could theoretically safely consume 12.7 kg (adult) or 3.6 kg (child) of that maize daily before reaching the WHO recommended maximum limit.

Although the measured grain U concentrations do not indicate an immediate dietary hazard based on the simple screening comparison used here, they remain relevant because maize is a widely consumed staple and fertilizer-derived U inputs are potentially chronic and cumulative.

3.5. Uranium and calcium linkage

Across both experiments, U generally decreased from soil to vegetative tissues and was lowest in grain, consistent with U being strongly retained by soils and showing limited phloem mobility compared with essential nutrients. The field dataset shows grain U on the order of 10^{-1} mg kg^{-1} , whereas the pot dataset shows grain U near or below the detection limit, highlighting that pot systems can suppress effective translocation to grain probably due to constrained rooting volume, altered water fluxes, and incomplete grain filling relative to field conditions. In a comparable maize/wheat field study (Stojanović et al., 2013), grain U was reported below detection (<0.01 mg kg^{-1}) after plants were washed, dried, and burned/ashed prior to measurement, illustrating that very low grain values are plausible under some soil and methodological contexts.

Because previous mechanistic studies (Sarhou et al., 2022) suggest that Ca transport pathways can influence U uptake, Ca was measured here as contextual information alongside U. However, the present study did not directly test uptake pathways or U speciation. In our field dataset, soil Ca and U covary positively (consistent with fertilizer-driven co-inputs and soil geochemistry), while within plant tissues the Ca-U association trends negative, consistent with the idea that higher Ca status and Ca competition at uptake sites can reduce net U entry and its subsequent translocation. The directionality is compatible with broader observations that nutrient cations (including Ca) regulate uptake of non-essential elements and radionuclides (Stojanović et al., 2013).

4. Conclusions

The study quantified U and Ca in soil and maize (*Zea mays* L.) using paired field as well as pot experiments in Tanzania. Three different fertilizers with contrasting compositions (Minjingu Powder, Nafaka Plus, YaraMila Cereal) as well as a control group without fertilization were considered. In the field experiments, U ranged from 2.07–3.96 mg kg⁻¹ in soil and 0.09–0.26 mg kg⁻¹ in grain, with intermediate concentrations in roots (0.99–2.20 mg kg⁻¹), stems (0.39–1.09 mg kg⁻¹) and leaves (0.17–0.48 mg kg⁻¹). These values confirm a consistent partitioning pattern soil > root > stem ≈ leaf > grain, indicating strong soil retention and limited translocation to edible tissues.

In the pot experiments, soil and root U remained measurable (soil up to 6.21 mg kg⁻¹, roots up to 3.66 mg kg⁻¹), whereas grain U was mostly at or near the analytical detection limit. Statistical analysis showed highly significant treatment effects for U in soil, root, stem and leaf compartments, and strong fertilizer/amendment interactions within the fertilized pots. In particular, the combined kaolin and tree bark sawdust treatment was associated with marked reductions in root and shoot U in several fertilizer treatments. These findings support the potential of low-cost amendments as a promising mitigation approach under controlled pot conditions, while also highlighting the need for confirmation under field-relevant conditions. Although several amendment treatments were associated with lower U concentrations in roots and shoots, the present study did not directly assess sorption capacity, soil-solution U, or U speciation. The observed reduction in tissue U and the corresponding transfer coefficients therefore support a preliminary mitigation interpretation, but the underlying mechanism remains unresolved. The combined kaolin and tree bark sawdust treatment was most consistently associated with reduced U transfer beyond the root compartment, suggesting that low-cost amendments may merit further investigation as practical retention measures in fertilizer-amended systems.

Ca showed the expected nutrient-like behavior (higher relative partitioning to aboveground tissues and grain than U), but the Ca-U relationship reported here should be interpreted cautiously because this study did not directly test uptake pathways or U speciation. Overall, the measured field grain U concentrations fall within published ranges for fertilized cereals, yet the upper values still justify follow-up work on maize-based exposure scenarios and on amendment performance under replicated field conditions.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Nils Haneklaus: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Dennis A. Mwalongo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Najat K. Mohammed:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Formal analysis. **Jacob B. Lisuma:** Writing – review & editing, Validation,

Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Hendrik Brink:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Hupenyu A. Mupambwa:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Hamid Mazouz:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Viktoriia Chubur:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Hynek Roubík:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Guangfei Qu:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis. **Stanisław Wacławek:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Formal analysis. **Kelvin M. Mtei:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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